

EVALUATION OF PROPOSED IEC REVERBERATION CHAMBER METHODOLOGY FOR RADIATED EMISSIONS MEASUREMENTS USING A REFERENCE RADIATOR

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ABSTRACT

This work evaluates the reverberation chamber methodology proposed for radiated emissions testing in the IEC draft standard 61000-4-21. Testing was conducted using a reference radiator system. Evaluations of the reference radiator were accomplished using in-band antennas. The results were compared to the measured output power of the reference radiator connected directly to a spectrum analyzer.

INTRODUCTION

As reverberation chambers become available as an alternative test procedure in various standards, there is increased interest in evaluating the proposed test methodology. Comparing test results obtained via the proposed standards with known or accepted measurement practices provide valuable information to individuals or committees responsible for the generation of such standards.

While direct comparisons are difficult due to different test environments, emissions testing does offer the ability to compare to a known source. By using a known source, the accuracy and limitations of a given methodology can be evaluated.

This investigation measured the emissions, both conducted and radiated, from a commercially available reference radiator [1]. The reference radiator was configured to generate radio frequency (RF) signals at 5 MHz spacing over its operating bandwidth. Three baluns were supplied with the reference radiator. Two were for interfacing with dipole and loop antennas supplied with the unit. The third was fitted with a type N connector which facilitated interfacing the unit directly to antennas and/or measurement instrumentation. For this paper we will focus on emissions measurements made with a log periodic antenna and a dual ridged horn antenna connected to the reference radiator. Testing

entailed attaching the reference radiator to the appropriate in-band antenna, which was supported on a phenolic tripod. These emissions were then compared to the conducted emission measurements taken by coupling the unit directly to a spectrum analyzer. Testing was performed over a frequency range of 80 MHz to 2500 MHz, using the mode tuned test methodology set forth in a draft version of the IEC 61000-4-21, Annex E [2]. Annex B [2] of this specification details reverberation chamber calibration procedures. Future references will be to either annex, reference to the parent document is implied. Measurements were taken on both the maximum and average received power over one tuner rotation. Only the maximum values will be discussed in this paper.

TEST FACILITY CALIBRATION

This test was conducted in a 5.51m x 5.21m x 3.38m reverberation chamber located at the Naval Surface Warfare Center, Dahlgren Va. depicted in Figure 1. The facility was calibrated in November 2000 in accordance with Annex B [2]. This calibration procedure collected field probe data (peak data only) as well as chamber input power and recorded the maximum and mean received power from a reference antenna placed within the working volume. The probe data was used to determine field uniformity. The probe data and chamber input power was used to determine the chamber calibration. The average received power is used to determine loading effects that may be caused by items under test. As shown in Figure 2, the measurement locations used for the calibration outline the "volume of uniform field" or a "working volume". Probe data was collected from the eight locations that form the corners of the working volume. Each time the probe was moved to a new location the receiving antenna was also moved to a new location within the working volume. The orientation of the receive antenna relative to the chamber axes was also changed at least 20 degrees relative to each axis at each position. This ensured that any bias in the field was detected.

Figure 1 (Test Configuration)

Figure 2 (Working Volume)

The field uniformity depends on the number of tuner positions (N) used to collect the data. For a relatively modest number of tuner steps a reasonably uniform field can be obtained [3]. This is true for overmoded cavities. All chambers will have a frequency at which they are no longer overmoded. This frequency is primarily dependent on chamber size. Therefore, all chambers will, at some point, become unusable as a reverberation chamber. Table 1 lists the number of tuner steps used for conducting the calibration and testing.

Table 1

Frequency range	Number of tuner steps
80 to 300 MHz	50
300 to 400 MHz	20
400 to 600 MHz	16
600 to 1000 MHz	12
1000 to 1500 MHz	12
1500 to 2000 MHz	12
2000 to 2500 MHz	12

The goal of a reverberation chamber is to generate a uniform field, within some bounded uncertainty, for all locations within the defined working volume. Results of this calibration show the facility to have a lowest usable frequency (LUF) of 150 MHz (Figure 3); therefore, data below 150 MHz is subject to errors greater than allowed by the specifications.

Figure 3 (Standard Deviation of Normalized E-Field Measurements)

Loading Measurements:

Prior to conducting any test in a reverberation chamber a loading evaluation must be performed. (There is always a possibility that the equipment under test may absorb energy from the test environment). As defined in Annex B.2 [2], locating the device within the working volume of the chamber and injecting a signal of known amplitude accomplish this. Stepping the tuner(s) and recording the amplitude of the received signal for the required number of samples will yield the average amplitude over a rotation. From this data the chamber calibration factor (CCF) was obtained. The CCF is defined as:

$$CCF = \left\langle \frac{P_{Avg Rec}}{P_{Inpu}} \right\rangle_n \quad (1)$$

According to Annex B.2 [2], this procedure must be performed for a minimum of one location of the receive antenna. For this evaluation the measurements were conducted at three locations in order to obtain more accurate results (n=3). This data was compared to data obtained during the initial empty chamber calibration to determine if any loading existed.

A similar factor, the empty chamber antenna calibration factor (ACF), was obtained during the initial chamber calibration (Annex B.1.2 [2]) and is defined as:

$$ACF = \left\langle \frac{P_{AvgRec}}{P_{Inpu}} \right\rangle_8 \quad (2)$$

The ACF data from the initial chamber calibration was obtained for each of eight locations. Provided that CCF does not exceed the measured uniformity of the ACF measurements, there is no need to correct for loading effects, in which case a chamber-loading factor (CLF) of 1 is applied. This comparison is depicted in Figure 4. Should the CCF exceed the uniformity described, the chamber is considered loaded and a CLF needs to be determined. The CLF is simply the ratio of the CCF and the ACF and is expressed as:

$$CLF = \frac{CCF}{ACF} \quad (3)$$

Figure 4 (ACF CCF Comparison)

The guidance given by Annex E [2] and Annex B.2 [2] calls for the loading evaluation to be conducted at "each test frequency". For most emissions tests, the output frequencies of the device to be tested are an unknown until after the test. Since no loading was anticipated from the reference radiator, and to expedite testing, it was decided to conduct the loading evaluation at the same frequencies used in the initial chamber calibration. As written, the specification is vague as to the number of frequencies to be used in conducting the

loading evaluation for emission testing, leaving this to the test planner. As shown in Figure 4, 15 out of 54 frequencies evaluated above 150 MHz exceed those measured during the initial chamber calibration. Figure 4 also shows that the CCF points which exceed the ACF data did so by a small margin both above and below the uniformity spread, this is indicative of measurement uncertainty and may not be due to EUT loading. Since CLF corrections are made relative to the mean ACF, a small deviation may result in relatively large correction. A positive value for the loading factor indicates a decrease in loading. While it is not likely that a device such as the reference radiator can affect the chamber in such a manner, it is possible that a few of the measurement points will fall outside the initial chamber calibration data when no loading exists. This is due to the uncertainties associated with the measurement process. In order to minimize this effect the standard recommends taking measurements at multiple measurement locations as was done for this evaluation. Uncertainties that contribute to this difference include cable and connector calibrations as well as receiver accuracy and linearity. The authors decided not to correct the data for chamber loading until it could be determined if the data truly indicated loading existed or if the excursions were the result of measurement uncertainties.

TEST METHODOLOGY

Prior to conducting an emissions test in a reverberation chamber, decisions must be made relative to the frequency spans, sweep times and number of samples (tuner steps) required for accurate measurements.

It is almost always desirable to utilize the fastest sweep time and narrowest resolution and video bandwidths possible. Since the output of the reference radiator was known and is constant, selection of the measurement settings was simplified. A sweep time of 50ms, a video bandwidth of 100 kHz and a resolution bandwidth of 300 kHz provided sufficient resolution and dynamic range for this experiment. The start and stop frequency and number of samples taken is depicted in Table 1. Each span consisted of 601 data points, resulting in 4207 data points over the test spectrum. The number of tuner samples used is mandated to be the same as in the chamber calibration.

PROCEDURES

Conducted Emissions:

The reference radiator is ideally suited for comparison measurements as it can be configured with a type N output connector allowing its output to be measured directly. By installing a 30dB attenuator in line, the output was measured using the same receiver settings as used for radiated measurements (Figure 5). These measurements were used as a comparison baseline. Conducted emissions are depicted in Figure 6. Due to the nature of the generated signal, graphical representation of the data ranges from the receiver noise floor to the maximum detected signal every 5 MHz. For clarity the data was processed to display the maximum measured signal over a running 5 MHz window. Figure 7 depicts this windowed trace for the conducted emission data. This 5 MHz windowing is used on all subsequent data traces as well.

Figure 5 (Conducted Emissions Setup)

Figure 6 (Conducted Emissions)

Figure 7 (Conducted Emissions With 5 MHz Max Windowing)

Radiated Emissions:

The emissions data were obtained by configuring the reference radiator with the desired antenna (log periodic below 1 GHz, Figure 8, dual ridge horn above 1GHz, Figure 9). Each frequency band was swept, storing the resultant amplitude trace. By repeating this for the required number of samples (tuner steps) and extracting the maximum of all samples, the maximum emissions were determined. That data was then corrected for cable losses and calculations for radiated power values were performed in accordance with Annex E.5 [2].

Figure 8 (EUT Attached To Log Periodic Antenna)

Figure 9 (EUT Attached To Dual Ridge Horn)

The expression for determining the radiated power based on the maximum measured receive power is as follows:

$$P_{\text{Radiated}} = \frac{P_{\text{MaxRec}} * \eta_{\text{Tx}}}{\text{CLF} * \text{IL}} \quad (3)$$

Where:

P_{MaxRec} is the maximum received power measured.

η_{Tx} is the antenna efficiency of the Tx antenna used during the initial chamber calibration. This efficiency is assumed to be 0.75 for log periodic antennas and 0.9 for horn antennas.

CLF is the chamber-loading factor.

IL (insertion loss) is ratio of maximum received power to the average input power during the initial chamber calibration (Annex B.1.3 [2]).

Since there are 97 calibration frequencies and 4207 frequencies within the test spectrum, it was necessary to extrapolate between the calibration frequencies to obtain the insertion loss and CLF for all data points.

Results

Since the EUT was configured with the same balun for the conducted emissions and antenna emissions measurements, a comparison of the data should demonstrate the accuracy of this measurement methodology. Figure 10 shows both the conducted and radiated emissions as well as the delta between the two (Radiated-Conducted).

As indicated in Figure 10 the overall variation was 16.0 dB, ranging from 6.3 dB to 9.7 dB above and below the

conducted data respectively. Figure 11 is an error distribution plot of delta between conducted and radiated emission measurements for both of the antennas used in testing. This data indicates that the measurements trend to the low side; however, the overall agreement is well within the bounds one can expect in a test of this nature.

Figure 10 (Emissions Comparison)

Figure 11 (Cumulative Error Distribution)

Conclusions

Agreement between the conducted measurements and the radiated measurements was good. The difference between the two was within the expected field uniformity of the reverberation chamber. As shown in Figure 11, the largest errors resulted at the lower frequencies where the log periodic antenna was used. Frequencies above 1 GHz, using the dual ridge horn, show much better agreement between conducted and radiated emission values. This indicates that reverberation chambers can be used to make accurate radiated power measurements.

Due to the relatively large number of measurements taken during the initial chamber calibration, resultant

chamber uniformity is very good. Comparing a single measurement location for determination of the CLF appears insufficient. Three locations were used for this evaluation and 15 of the calibration frequencies exceeded the values obtained during the initial chamber calibration. The deviations from the initial calibration were small, ranging from -2.37dB to + 1.03 dB. After consulting with the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) [4], it was determined that these deviations do not exceed that which should be expected. Based on these findings and additional consultations with NIST [4] it is recommended that 1) the standard be changed to require a three location CCF evaluation as a minimum and 2) reevaluate the methodology of determining when the CLF should be applied.

[4] Personal communications with John Ladbury, National Institute of Standards and Technology, Boulder, CO.

The data also shows that considerable care must be taken in order to minimize measurement uncertainties. Small changes in the measurement system such as cable losses and system drift can have significant impact.

The standard provides a basic approach to conducting emissions measurements using reverberation chambers. More guidance is needed in how many frequencies should be used for the loading evaluation.

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References

[1] Reference radiator (RefRad™) EMCO Model 4630 was used for this evaluation. Use of the RefRad™ does not constitute an endorsement of this product.

[2] Draft IEC 61000-4-21 *Electromagnetic Compatibility (EMC) – Part 4: Testing and Measurement Techniques Section 21: Reverberation Chambers* IEC/SC77B/CISPR/A Reverberation Chambers Joint Task Force, draft November 2000, Document Numbers CISPR/A/285/CD and 773/304/DC.

[3] Hatfield, M.O. "A Calibration Procedure for Reverberation Chambers", 2000 IEEE International Symposium on EMC, Washington DC, August 2000